

IMPROVING STUDENT BEHAVIOR OF GRADE-9 IN THE CLASSROOM THROUGH MIND-RELAXING ACTIVITIES: BASIS FOR ITS INTEGRATION INTO THE EDUCATION CURRICULUM

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine whether mind-relaxing activities are effective in improving the behavior of students and if these activities can be integrated into an education set-up. The study also wants to solve the behavioral issues of the students using these mind-relaxing activities, with the initiative coming from faculty researchers. The methodology involves conducting three-week mind-relaxing activities, followed by a survey to gauge such behavioral changes. Grade 9 students from three different sections were selected to be the respondents. A behavioral rating checklist was used to compare the perspective of students and teachers on the effect of mind-relaxing activities. Results show an increase in the perspective of the students in behavior from the first (24.33) to the second week (26.27) but showed a decrease in score from the second (26.67) to the third week (24.67). It is also notable that there is an increase in the perspective of the teachers in behavior from the first (23.92) to the second week (23.81) but showed a decreased score from the second (23.81) to the third week (26.46). Finally, the computed t-statistic which is lower than the tabulated t-statistic, indicates that there exists no statistically significant difference in the perspective of the students and teachers in terms of the effectiveness of mind-relaxing activities in promoting positive behavior. These findings depict the possible importance of using these mind-relaxing activities to conduct a learning environment among students to improve their behavior.

Keywords: *integration, mind-learning activities, behavior management, positive behavioral outcomes*

INTRODUCTION

Academic pressures and social expectations usually weigh heavily on the students, and addressing their emotional well-being for holistic education is paramount due to the fact-paced world. According to Greenberg and Harris (2012), incorporating mind-body techniques into the educational system not only enhances emotional regulation but also enhances cognitive functions and overall well-being. These interventions may nurture mindfulness in youth and children and be a feasible and effective method of resilience-building and treating disorders in clinical populations. Further, as teachers, managing descriptive behavior or dealing with unruly children throughout the school day are all tasks that must be completed despite not being explicitly mentioned in their job specifications. In addition, to help eliminate this disrespectful behavior among students, some educators from local and international contexts conduct different mind-relaxing activities for the students to prevent burnout and academic stress.

According to Scott (2024), music education involves focusing one's attention and awareness on one's breath as he/she meditates and listens to music. Meditation was considered a mindfulness practice that involves focusing attention on a particular sensation, sound, mantra, image, and other focal point. Music can be a helpful tool to generate a great state of relaxation. Meditation music can include relaxing music specifically designed to help people get into a meditative state, as well as any music that is enjoyable. It can also demonstrate the efficacy of mindfulness in reducing stress and enhancing attention and self-awareness, (Shapiro et.al., 2011)

Meanwhile, journaling mind-body was considered to have therapeutic benefits, facilitating emotional processing and self-disclosure through the utilization of expressive writing (Pennebaker & Smyth, 2016). Research also suggests a wide range of physical, cognitive, and emotional benefits from expressive writing (Baikie & Wilhelm, 2005). Journaling can also significantly help to accept rather than judge one's mental experiences, which may result in fewer negative emotions in response to the stressors (Ford et al., 2018; Baikie & Wilhelm, 2005).

Furthermore, drawing and coloring activities have been recognized for their therapeutic value in promoting one's emotional well-being and reducing anxiety, as stated by Stuckey & Nobel (2010), since color affects behavior, as well as performance, intentions and cognitive abilities (Kumi et al., 2013), while some scholars mentioned that colors might help learners to increase their arousal. A study conducted by Plass, Heidig, Hayward, Homer, and Um (2014) reveals that warm colors, such as yellow and orange, instead of cold colors, such as gray, used in materials can also enhance the learning of the students.

With this, the researchers want to determine if integrating these evidence-based mind-body activities into the educational curriculum will enhance not only the academic performance of their students, but also their resilience and emotional intelligence to face the complexities of life beyond their classrooms. Through this approach to the educational curriculum, St. Joseph School of Gagalangin reaffirms its big commitment to the better

development of its students, preparing them not only for academic success but also for personal fulfillment and well-being. These activities will be administered from the 3rd week of November until the 1st week of December, then will go to test if there exists a significant difference in the observation of the teachers and students on the effectiveness of these mind-relaxing activities.

Research Questions

This study's primary purpose is to determine the impact of mind-relaxing activities on improving of junior high school students' behavior. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a significant difference in the behavior of students after experiencing mind-relaxing activities based on the observations of:
 - a. the students/participants;
 - b. their Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH) teacher?
2. Is there a significant difference among students' assessment of their behavior in their MAPEH classes during the three-week period?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study: The research locale of this study is the St. Joseph School, Manila.

Sampling Method: The study employed a probability sampling technique, specifically cluster sampling. The Grade 9 students at St. Joseph School, Manila, were selected, and all sections (San Lorenzo Ruiz, St. Ignatius of Loyola, and St. Frances de Chantal) were included in the study.

Respondents: The respondents of the study are all the students of the three sections of Grade 9 of St. Joseph School, Manila. There is a total of 102 students/respondents for the three sections.

Data Gathering Procedure:

A. *Intervention: Mind-relaxing activities*

The researchers conducted different mind-relaxing activities, which were adopted from Mind-body Skills: Activities for Emotional Regulation by the National Institute for Trauma and Loss in Children (2014). The activities ran weekly and were suited for the given level and age of the participants. In the first week, the researchers conducted the first activity entitled "Mindfulness," where the students listened to music as they closed their eyes and relaxed their minds for five (5) minutes before the class started. In the second week, the students participated in "Journaling Mind-body Exercises." In this activity, the students were given five (5) minutes to write a letter to the chosen people in their lives. Lastly, the "Drawing and coloring"

where the students were given a piece of paper with a corresponding shape on it. The students freely applied their desired colors to the shapes on the paper. The three activities were conducted five (5) minutes before the start of the class.

B. Survey Questionnaire: Self-assessment of behavior

The survey was conducted on the students immediately after the mind-relaxing activity. The mind-relaxing activities were conducted once a week for three weeks to compare the perspective of students and teachers on the effect of mind-relaxing activities. A self-made behavioral rating checklist was prepared and used for the actual data gathering. The questions were subjected to validation by three (3) experts: (1) Dr. Conrado F. Vidal – Dean, College of Arts and Sciences; (2) Mr. Elfie Samaniego – Faculty, Psychology Department; and (3) Mr. Joshua Urrete – Faculty, Languages and Humanities Department. After the validation, the instrument was subjected to reliability testing using Cronbach's Alpha. The instrument exhibited a good internal consistency with a Cronbach's Alpha level of 0.814. The survey questions are as follows (rated using a three-point Likert scale; 1 for Poor, 2 for Satisfactory and 3 for Very Satisfactory). The items used were as follows:

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE 1 (To be assessed/answered by the students)

1. I am excited to attend MAPEH class
2. I participate actively in class activities
3. I give close attention to the lesson
4. I listen attentively to the teacher
5. I am restful in seat without unnecessary noise
6. I relate well with classmates
7. I relate well with the teacher
8. I use time wisely in class
9. I come prepared
10. I pass in the quiz / test

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE 2 (To be assessed/answered by the teachers)

1. The student is excited to attend MAPEH class.
2. The student participates actively in class activities.
3. The student gives close attention to the lesson.
4. The student listens attentively to the teacher.
5. The student is restful in the seat without unnecessary noise.
6. The student relates well with classmates.
7. The student relates well with the teacher.
8. The student uses time wisely in class.
9. The student comes to class prepared.
10. The student passes the quiz/test.

Process of Analysis: For the statistical analysis of the study, one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to determine if mind-relaxing activities have a significant effect on student's behavior as perceived by the students themselves and their teachers. On the other hand, an independent t-test was used to determine if there exists a significant difference between the responses of the teacher and the students.

Scope and Limitations: The scope of the study is the students in St. Joseph School, Manila, but is only delimited to all (three) sections of the 9th Grade.

RESULTS

**SOP 1: Is there a significant difference in the behavior of students after experiencing mind-relaxing activities based on the observations of:
a. the students/participants;**

Table 1. Test of Significant Effect of Mind-Relaxing Activities to the Student's Behavior
as
Perceived by the Students Themselves

Student	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Week 1	24.28	3.14	28.94	0.00	Significantly Different
Week 2	24.11	2.77			
Week 3	26.73	2.68			

Table 1 presents the mean or average student behavior scores as perceived by the students for each week of the mind-relaxing activities. Based on the table, the behavioral scores from week 1 (24.28) have a slight decrease in week 2 (24.11) but recorded a big increase in week 3 (26.73). The difference between these three weeks of mind-relaxing activities was found to be statistically significant, as provided by the results of the one-way ANOVA ($F = 28.94$, $p = 0.00$) since the p-value is less than the significance level of 0.05.

**Research Question 1: Is there a significant difference in the behavior of students after experiencing mind-relaxing activities based on the observations of:
a. the teachers;**

Table 2. Test of Significant Effect of Mind-Relaxing Activities to the Student’s Behavior as Perceived by the Teachers

Teacher	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Week 1	24.33	2.31	2.05	0.21	Not Significantly Different
Week 2	24.67	1.54			
Week 3	26.67	0.58			

Table 2 presents the mean or average student behavior scores as perceived by the students for each week of the mind relaxing activities. Based on the table, the behavioral scores from week 1 (24.33) have a with slight increase in week 2 (24.67) and recorded a big increase in week 3 (26.67). The difference between these three weeks of mind-relaxing activities were found to be statistically not significant as provided by the results of the one-way ANOVA ($F = 2.05$, $p = 0.21$) since the p-value is greater than the significance level of 0.05.

Research Question 2. Is there a significant difference among students’ assessment of their behavior in their MAPEH classes during the three-week period?

Table 3. Test of Significant Difference on the Perceived Mind-Relaxing Activities of the Students and Teachers

Respondents	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Students	25.04	3.10	-0.18	0.86	Not Significantly Different
Teachers	25.22	1.72			

Table 3 presents the mean or average student behavior scores as perceived by the students and teachers for the three-week mind-relaxing activities. Based on the table, there exists no significant difference between students (25.04) and teachers (25.22) since the p-value is greater than the significance level of 0.05.

DISCUSSION

Conclusions

Based on the results provided in the previous part of this research, we can conclude that even though the students perceived that their behavior had improved (Table 1), the teachers were not able to observe it (Table 2). This is because the two groups have different perceptions, but these perceptions do not have significant differences (Table 3).

Recommendations

The study was conducted to determine whether mind-relaxing activities effectively improve students' behavior and if these activities can be integrated into an education setup. The results showed an increase in the perspectives of both the students and the teachers; therefore, the researchers believe the need to incorporate these mind-relaxing activities to conduct a learning environment among students to improve their behavior.

Future studies may venture on the following recommendations. In terms of its integration into the curriculum, future researchers may explore how mind-relaxing activities can be practiced in the classrooms as an official or institutional program of the school to avoid disrupting the flow of classes and the academic calendar. Creating mind-relaxing programs with specific guidelines and frameworks will benefit not only students but also teaching and non-teaching staff, as they will have a guide on how the activities will be implemented in a strategic and structured process. Similarly, future research may look into the effects of demographics such as gender, age, nationality, and other socioeconomic factors that could influence how these interventions. It had been noted in the study that in the second to third weeks of the implementation, both teachers and students had a decrease in their perception of the behavior; therefore, future studies may identify the significant impact of duration and frequency of relaxing activities per week. It is also recommended that researchers study the impact of the time of the school day when to implement the activities. Ideally, there should also be workshops for educators on how to properly implement the process based on a set of guidelines in order to have monitoring and evaluation of the activities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the entirety of the study, which involves human participants, ethical protocols were rigorously observed to safeguard the confidentiality and privacy of all participants. Before the conduct of the mind-relaxing activities and other data collection procedures, an approval letter to conduct research was signed by the school in accordance with the established research ethics guidelines stated by the Office of the Principal. The consent process ensured that participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Moreover, the researchers briefed the participants on their voluntary involvement in the study and that they could withdraw anytime without any penalties or effects on their academics. The study adhered to all ethical standards and upheld the integrity of all research data-gathering procedures.

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